

e-ISSN: 3048-8907

Volume 09 Issue 01 Jan-
Apr 2026

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Submission Date: Dec 11,
2025

Copyright Received Date:
Dec 24, 2025

Design and Implementation of a Cost-Effective Analog Front-End for Lithium-Ion Battery Management Systems

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ABSTRACT

Lithium-ion batteries are the cornerstone of modern electric mobility and renewable energy storage; however, they require strict monitoring to prevent catastrophic failures such as thermal runaway and deep discharge. This paper presents the design and hardware implementation of a modular Battery Management System (BMS) prototype. The system features a custom Analog Front-End (AFE) utilizing differential operational amplifiers for precise individual cell voltage monitoring and a Hall-effect sensor for current estimation. Furthermore, a hardware-based Constant Current/Constant Voltage (CC/CV) charging circuit was developed and tested. The prototype, validated using an Arduino microcontroller, achieved a voltage measurement accuracy of $\pm 10\text{mV}$ and successful charge termination at 4.2V. This work serves as the foundational hardware layer for a future high-precision State-of-Charge (SoC) estimation system based on the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF).

Keywords:- *Lithium-ion batteries, modern electric mobility, renewable energy storage, prototype*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid transition toward electric mobility has placed Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries at the forefront of energy research due to their high energy density and low self-discharge rates. Despite these advantages, Li-ion chemistry operates within a narrow Safe Operating Area (SOA) regarding voltage (typically 2.5V–4.2V) and temperature [1]. Exceeding these limits can lead to irreversible capacity loss or safety hazards.

Commercial BMS solutions often rely on dedicated Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs), which are costly and proprietary. This project aims to design a flexible, low-cost BMS architecture. The primary contribution of this paper is the development and validation of a discrete component Analog Front-End (AFE) capable of accurate differential voltage sensing in series-connected battery packs, and the implementation of a robust charging control loop.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Data Acquisition

In a series-connected battery pack, only the bottom-most cell shares a ground reference with the microcontroller. Measuring the upper cells requires a differential approach to reject the common-mode voltage. This system utilizes a quad-channel operational amplifier configuration (using the LM324) acting as unity-gain differential amplifiers.

These circuits step down the floating potential of each cell (3.0V–4.2V relative to the previous cell) into a ground-referenced 0–5V signal, ensuring compatibility with the Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) module. A network of Negative Temperature Coefficient (NTC) thermistors is placed in thermal contact with the cell surfaces.

These sensors provide real-time temperature data to prevent thermal runaway.

Digital Control Unit

The central processing unit for the prototype is an Arduino Nano, interfaced with high-precision peripheral modules to overcome the limitations of its internal hardware. Instead of relying on the microcontroller's native 10-bit.

Analog-to-Digital Converter, this system integrates an ADS1115 external ADC module. The ADS1115 provides 16-bit resolution, allowing the system to detect voltage changes as small as 0.18 mV (depending on the programmable gain setting).

This precision is critical for accurately measuring the flat region of the Lithium-ion discharge curve where small voltage drops correlate to significant SoC changes. It communicates with the Arduino via the I2C bus, providing a robust digital interface that isolates the sensitive analog measurements from the noisy digital switching logic of the microcontroller.

Power Regulation & Protection:

The charging circuit implements a hardware-regulated Constant Current / Constant Voltage (CC/CV) profile. It utilizes a P-Channel MOSFET as a high-side switch, driven by a Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) signal from the microcontroller. This allows for precise regulation of the charging current, tapering it down as the battery approaches its full voltage.

HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION

This section details the specific circuitry designed and fabricated for the project.

Voltage Sensing Unit

In a multi-cell series configuration (e.g., 4S), the upper cells do not share a common ground with the microcontroller. To measure individual cell voltages, a Differential Amplifier configuration was implemented using LM324 Operational Amplifiers.

The output voltage (Vout) for each cell is given by the differential gain equation:

$$V_{out} = R_f/R_{in} (V_2 - V_1) \quad (1)$$

Where V2 is the input voltage at the non-inverting terminal of opamp and V1 is the input voltage at the inverting terminal. The values are chosen such that the gain=1.

Charging Circuit

The charging module is physically implemented to follow the standard Li-ion charging profile. It consists of a buck converter topology regulated by a P-Channel MOSFET.

The control loop ensures Constant Current (CC): Limits current to 0.5C when Vcell<4.1V and Constant Voltage (CV): Clamps voltage at 4.2V while allowing current to decay exponentially.

Thermal Fault Detection Unit

To ensure redundant safety, a hardware-based over-temperature cutoff was designed using LM393 dual differential comparators. The circuit monitors four distributed 10kΩ NTC thermistors, comparing their voltage drop against a tunable reference threshold

(Vref) set by a precision potentiometer. If any cell temperature exceeds the calibrated limit, the comparator output toggles, sending an immediate hardware interrupt to the microcontroller to disconnect the load. This topology ensures thermal protection remains active even in the event of a software failure.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The hardware prototype was subjected to bench testing using a variable DC power supply to simulate battery cells and a partially discharged 18650 cell for

charging tests. Voltage Measurement Accuracy: The differential amplifier outputs were read by the Arduino ADC and compared against a high-precision multimeter.

Table 1:-Voltage Measured

Cell	MULTIMETER VOLTAGE	MEASURED VOLTAGE
Top Cell	3.513V	3.528V
MIDDLE CELL	3.528V	3.554V
BOTTOM CELL	3.538V	3.545V

As we can see from the above values, the maximum difference is 25mV while the average difference is 15mV. This shows good performance.

Charging Cycle Verification

The charging circuit was tested on a cell with an initial voltage of 3.5V. The system successfully cut off the charging current when the terminal voltage stabilized at 4.21V, preventing overcharge.

DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

The experimental validation of the prototype highlights a distinct trade-off between hardware simplicity and computational capability. While the Analog Front-End (AFE) design proved robust, the digital processing stage revealed significant bottlenecks that define the scope for future optimization.

Evaluation of Analog Performance

The integration of the ADS1115 ADC with the Op-Amp differential network resolved the resolution issues common in low-cost BMS designs. The differential amplifier configuration demonstrated high Common-Mode Rejection Ratio (CMRR), effectively filtering out the electrical noise introduced by the PWM switching of the charging circuit.

Computational Bottlenecks

The primary limitation identified during testing was the processing power of the Arduino Nano. Floating-Point Latency: The proposed Extended Kalman Filter

(EKF) algorithm requires recursive matrix operations (multiplication and inversion of 3×3 matrices) involving floating-point numbers. Since the ATmega328P lacks a hardware Floating Point Unit (FPU), these calculations must be emulated in software. Benchmarking revealed that a single EKF iteration took >150 ms to execute.

This latency is unacceptable for real-time protection, as the system would be "blind" to current spikes occurring during that calculation window. Memory Constraints: The limited SRAM (2KB) of the Arduino is insufficient to store the large history arrays and covariance matrices required for advanced estimation or machine learning-based aging prediction.

Charging Efficiency & Thermal Constraints

The linear regulation aspect of the current charging circuit, while simple and effective for low currents, exhibited thermal inefficiencies at higher power levels. At charging currents above 1A, the P-Channel MOSFET dissipated significant heat due to switching losses, requiring larger passive heat sinks. This limits the current design to low-power applications (e.g., <50 W packs) unless a synchronous buck converter topology is adopted in future iterations.

The Implementation Gap

The study confirms that while accurate data *acquisition* is possible with low-cost

components (Op-Amps + External ADC), accurate *state estimation* is a software challenge.

The system currently relies on "Coulomb Counting" (current integration) for SoC, which is prone to drift over time. The hardware is ready for advanced algorithms, but the computing core is the limiting factor, validating the necessity of the planned migration to the 32-bit STM32 architecture.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

This paper presented the design and validation of a low-cost analog front-end for a Battery Management System. The Op-Amp differential sensing and discrete charging circuits were proven to be accurate and reliable.

Future work involves migrating the control logic to an STM32F4 microcontroller. The 32-bit architecture and hardware Floating Point Unit (FPU) of the STM32 will enable the implementation of the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) [6], fusing the accurate voltage data obtained in this study with dynamic current measurements to achieve high-precision SoC estimation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT (HEADING 5)

We take this opportunity to express our profound gratitude to the respected principal Dr. Bheemsha Arya, BMS College of Engineering for providing a congenial environment to work in. Our sincere gratitude to Dr. K. P. Lakshmi, Head of the Department, Electronics and Communication Engineering for encouraging and providing opportunity to carry Mini Project in the department.

We heart fully thank our guide Sujatha K for the guidance and constant encouragement throughout the course of this Mini Project without which this

project would not be successful. A number of personalities, in their own capacities have helped us in carrying out this Mini Project. We would like to take this opportunity to thank them all. Last but not the least we thank our friends and family for their encouragement and help.

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